

HARMONIC BASIS AND FACTURAL DESCRIPTION OF WORKS WRITTEN FOR PIANO AND ORCHESTRA

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Annotation: *The harmonic basis and textural description of the works written for piano and orchestra were covered through sheet music examples.*

Key words: *orchestra, agogy, passage, harmony, texture, dynamics.*

The concept of "technique" in the performance of the piano instrument has a broad meaning, i.e. the acquisition of high-quality sounds and the mastering of various methods of playing the piano, mastering the principles of using the pedal and appliqué, mastering the principles of arrangement, dynamic contrast, and agogics. When working on musical works, it is necessary to use certain methods and tools to perform the above main tasks. One of them is to work on the works step by step. These stages are conditional, and it is different for every performer. Step-by-step work allows students to carefully and gradually learn the musical language of the work, diligently overcome the difficulties of the work and create an artistic interpretation.

"Fantasia for Piano and Orchestra" of the great French composer K. Debussy acquires an artistically harmonious essence through its fundamental harmonic basis and complex technical performance aspects.

This fantasy by K. Debussy expresses the richness of passage and trio textures and the musical theme of the piano part of the work through the harmonic pedal. During the performance, horizontal and vertical control and generalization of orchestra lines is required.

The first acquaintance with the sheet music of the piano works of the composers of the French school consists of reading, understanding and first analyzing it. This work is necessary for the reader to feel the character of the play, to understand its main content, to pay attention to the difficulties encountered in it, aspects of expression. All the famous representatives of the piano school believed

that this stage should be carried out before directly studying the piece of music, and emphasized the need for thinking-hearing work during the initial work on the sheet music. The advantage of first working the works of composers of the French school, including K. Debussy, without an instrument is that the performer's attention is not divided into technical difficulties, at the same time, the musician's inner hearing helps to understand musical images, to experience a certain emotional state, to think about the richness of sounds in the work.

But this kind of thinking on the text is not true for the auditory reader. When working with students whose internal auditory skills are not sufficiently developed, it is necessary to start working on the piece with an instrument. Nevertheless, it should not be forgotten that it is possible to understand the artistic language of the work only by listening and mastering the musical basis by constantly using methods that activate the inner hearing and thinking of the student.

There are several types of music-theoretical analysis used when working on the pieces of the composers of the French school. For example, it can be learned from the style, genre, harmony and tone of the play. In these types of analysis, tasks are performed as follows:

- to determine which composer created this play and its place among other works of this genre;
- to know the main structure of the parts of the play, their compatibility with each other and the meaning of each part in general;
- to determine the thematic unity of the work, various contrasts, intermediate and auxiliary structures.

When working on pieces, students should never be given purely craft tasks (strokes, rhythms, appliqué, etc.). The search for means and methods of expression should

always be combined with the search for the best interpretation of an artistic image, and should be determined by the tasks of melodiousness, comprehensibility and emotional fullness of the content of the work. After studying the work in parts, the process of creating a complete performance and bringing it to the final pace begins. Issues of shape development and definition become more important when approaching real speed. Since music is an art performed in time intervals, the student's attention should be focused on the harmony of the parts in tempo and dynamics, the performance of high points, deviations from the tempo and returns to the previous tempo, the precise execution of pauses, etc. need The student should have a clear idea of the plan of the performance of the work, have some compact "complex" of its performance, be able to consciously notice the structure of phrases, sentences and parts, be able to hear the tone points and climaxes in individual parts, as well as in the whole work. In the repertoire of French music, series of variations occupy a significant place among large-scale works. Their uniqueness lies in the fact that vanational series combine the characteristics of both large and small forms. Therefore, the student will have different performance skills when working on these works. Each variation, like a miniature, has the ability to express the idea briefly and concisely, to say a lot in a short time. At the same time, certain problems arise when collecting all the individual variations and combining them into a large form.

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